

VUNOKLANG MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION

(Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola)

ISSN: 2276-8114

Website: www.vmjste.net

ASSESSMENT OF COMPETENCIES OF UNDERGRADUATE BUSINESS EDUCATION STUDENTS FOR ECONOMIC VALUE CREATION IN NORTH EAST NIGERIA

Gyongon Habu Gichi¹, Umar Inuwa² & Haruna Angulu³

^{1,2,&3}Department of Vocational and Technology Education, Faculty of Technology Education, Abubakar Tafawa
Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria.

Corresponding author: alumhari@gmail.com +2348069563101

Abstract

This study examined the competencies of undergraduate business education students for economic value creation in North East, Nigeria. The study had four specific objectives and four research questions which were meant to guide the study. The study adopted a survey research design that is purely quantitative, using structured questionnaires administered to 262 randomly selected manufacturing SMEs business Practitioners in North-Eastern Nigeria. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviations. The findings of the study revealed among others that creativity, innovative, problem solving and personnel management competencies are highly required for economic value creation among undergraduate business education students. Hence, the persistent raise in unemployment among business education graduates in North East as well Nigeria as a whole can be drastically reduced by inculcating these competencies to undergraduate business education students. The present study therefore, recommend that the regulatory bodies of tertiary institutions should ensure that business education students are well exposed to creativity, innovative, problem solving, and personnel management competencies to enable them to be self-reliance after graduation through economic value creation.

Keywords: Competencies, Undergraduate Business Education, Economic Value Creation

Introduction

Business education plays a significant role in Nigeria's economic growth and development. It improves personal qualities and builds the attitude of individuals that are necessary for adjustment to personal and employment situation, it provides knowledge, skills and competencies for individuals to function well in office occupation and create jobs for themselves and others (Amoor & Udoh 2018). Likewise, Nkamnebe (2008) on his part suggested that Business Education has potentials to help towards achieving national development in a number of ways. UNESCO (2014) also affirmed that Business Education is a master plan for national development by declaring thus: since education is considered the key to effective development strategies, Business Education must be the master key that can alleviate poverty, promote peace, and conserve the environment to improve the quality for all and help achieve sustainable national development.

Business Education prepares students for entering into and/or advancement in job within business and prepares them to handle their own business affairs and function intelligently in the production of goods and services (Akhere, 2013). Schweitzer (2016) was of the opinion that Business Education equips individuals with tools and techniques of successful handling of various businesses and contributing to global economy. Tominsion (2016) and Schweitzer (2016) outlined the followings as the functions of Business Education; development of mental and physical skill of an individual's, provision of goods and services, information acquisition, ecological development, socio

cultural change; improve nutrition and health, individual creativity. The authors maintained that these functions lead to national development. Oziengbe (2009) argued that Business Education enhances self-employment, technological improvement, high standard of living, self-reliance, consumer economic efficiency, man-power skill development among other.

Despite the numerous contributions of business education in Nigeria, it is observed that business education graduates are seen moving from one office to another in search of unavailable white-collar jobs and this increases the level of the country's unemployment (Maigida, 2012, Uddin 2013; Samuel 2020). The assertion of Maigida, (2012); Uddin (2013); Samuel (2020) also concurred with the argument of Ezenwafor, Faben, and Olaniyi (2016) that unemployment is on the increase in Nigeria. They further added that, tertiary institutions in Nigeria turns out thousands of graduates without corresponding job opportunities. The unemployment rate in Nigeria rose to 33.3% in the third quarter of 2020, which is an increase from 27.1% in the second quarter of 2020 (National Bureau of Statistic, 2021). The analysis of the National Bureau of Statistic, 2021 also revealed that north eastern states have the highest unemployment rate.

Mazzucato (2018) suggested that there is need for tertiary institutions graduates to possess essential competencies for value creation in order to become meaningful and self-reliant citizens and this will also lead to national economic growth and development. Value creation relate to the ways in which outputs are produced (production) and shared across the economy (distribution) as well as what is done with the earnings from this production (reinvestment). It is the productive transformation of raw materials into goods and services that creates wealth, which potentially can be distributed across society (Mazzucato, 2018). Value creation, improves production of goods and services, thereby creating job and reducing unemployment, that is why emerging economies' policies and programs are geared towards value creation. It is what makes the difference among developed, developing and underdeveloped economy (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development [OECD], 2019). Therefore, possessions of certain competencies are critical for value creation.

Recent literatures (Osisioma, 2015; Ezenwafor, Faben, & Olaniyi, 2016; Nwagwu, 2016; Okoye, 2017; Rubin & Dierdorff 2017) argued that creativity competencies, innovative competencies, problem solving competencies, and personnel management competencies are competencies that can enable individual to be value creators. It is in view of these arguments that this paper intends to assess the competencies of undergraduate business education students for value creation in north east Nigeria, with specific focus in creativity competencies, innovative competencies, problem solving competencies and personnel management competencies. The study's outcome will be relevant to the business education students of tertiary institutions in terms of identifying the competencies require for value creation.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study is to assess the competencies require by undergraduate business education for value creation in north east Nigeria. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Determine the level of creativity competencies of undergraduate business education students for value creation in North East Nigeria.
2. Determine the level of innovative competencies of undergraduate business education students for value creation in North East Nigeria.

3. Determine the level of problem-solving competencies of undergraduate business education students for value creation in North East Nigeria.
4. Find out the level of personnel management competencies of undergraduate business education students for value creation in North East Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated:

1. What is the level of creativity competencies of undergraduate business education students for value creation in North East Nigeria?
2. What is the level of innovative competencies of undergraduate business education students for value creation in North East Nigeria?
3. What is the level of problems solving competencies of undergraduate business education students for value creation in North East Nigeria?
4. What is the level of personnel management competencies of undergraduate business education students for value creation in North East Nigeria?

Literature Review

Concept of Competencies

Competencies are indispensable qualities that distinguish performance. Competencies in general are described as combined and integrated components of knowledge, skills, and attitudes (Kyndt & Baert, 2015). While the terms are linked, they are also distinct. Competency is a class of things that can be used to characterize individuals and their behaviours, whereas competence can be described as the evaluation of performance in a specific domain of activity (Mitchelmore & Rowley, 2010). The following discussion focuses on the issues related to competency. Competency includes knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and behaviours that are necessary to achieve the desired performance level in a particular activity or task (Morris, Webb, Fu, & Singhal, 2013). Some authors consider competencies as 'knowledge, skills, and attitudes that are necessary to perform a job successfully' (Miller, Wesley, & Williams, 2012). Others define it as characteristics in a field of knowledge, abilities, and attitudes that provide high quality task realisation (Filipowicz, 2004) or describe its attributes as abilities, intellectual capacities, and attitudes (Gupta & Roos, 2001). Recently, the terms 'professional' and 'generic' have been used to describe employees' competencies. The first group covers specific knowledge and skills needed for certain job positions, so these competencies are job-specific. The second groups (also called behavioural or social competencies) describe social and psychological abilities that influence an employee's workplace behaviour: for example, communication skills, problem-solving, or conflict resolution. However, it is impossible to define a single and final set of generic competencies (Young and Chapman, 2010) because they are applied in different professional contexts and beyond the field of study (Strijbos, Engels, & Struyven, 2015).

Generic competencies are not specific to any given job or work role they are generic in that they are critical for success across different job types (Young & Chapman, 2010). They are not related to a specific context and as a result, are potentially more easily transferred to other contexts (Nicolescu & Pacaronun 2009), one reason generic

competencies are relatively more important than specific competencies (Grosemans, Coertjens, & Kyndt, 2017; Heijke, Meng, & Ris, 2003). There are other interrelated terms that are used interchangeably in the literature: ‘skills’, ‘expertise’, or ‘acumen’ (Smith & Morse, 2005). Furthermore, generic skills generally refer to skills and attributes that are useful across different job and life contexts are also alternatively labelled in the literature as core skills, employability skills, life skills, soft skills, transferable skills, generic attributes, generic capabilities, workplace competencies, and key competencies (Male, 2010; Vucetic, 2018; Young & Chapman, 2010). Skills for operating a business enterprise are needed for the business to succeed in the competitive market. Skill is the ability to do something well and is usually gained through training or experience. Okoli (2013) defined skills as the economic tools with which entrepreneurs acquire and solve societal problems. Skills are practical activities which make one employable, self-reliant and relevant to the society. Okoli further stated that value creators must possess these business skills that are necessary to enable them start, their own business enterprises and market the products or services. Skills go a long way in helping entrepreneurs become successful. Skills are those activities that will enable an individual or organisation to manage his/her own enterprise.

Competencies play an extremely important role both in the workplace and the field of tertiary education (Pabian, Sima, & Kyncilova, 2011). Eliminating the gap between the levels of competencies demanded in today’s organisations and the knowledge traditionally passed to students in the course of their studies is a key issue for improving the efficiency of education systems in many countries. However, this will not be possible without ensuring quality academic staff to provide students with the current knowledge and skills necessary to succeed in the value creation driven world (Leoni, 2014). Employers also consider individual values and personalities, which are formed in the environment in which a person is raised, and the knowledge and skills obtained during the course of education. In large enterprises that employ more than 1,000 employees, knowledge and skills are more important. However, in small business entities, more attention is paid to personal traits and values. At the recruitment stage, the so-called generic competencies tend to be more important than specific ones (Cheong, Hill, Fernandez-Chung, & Leong, 2015).

Value Creation Competencies

The competencies that individuals need in order to successfully develop an idea into a thriving business are often termed value creation competencies (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2011; Markman, 2007; Man, 2007). Mitchelmore and Rowley, (2010) defines competency as “the willingness and ability to perform a task”. Sanchez (2011) defines competencies as “a cluster of related knowledge, traits, attitudes and skills that affect a major part of one’s job; that correlate with performance on the job; that can be measured against well accepted standards; and that can be improved via training and development”. Man *et al.* (2002) define value creation competencies as the total ability of the entrepreneur to perform a job successfully. To define value creation competencies, the three domains that must be considered are knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The knowledge domain, considered the basis of value creation competency, includes basics of entrepreneurship, value creation, idea generation, opportunities, accounting, finance, technology, marketing, risk, and other key concepts (Krueger, 2005). As for value creation skills, Fisher *et al.* (2008) defined a framework for analyzing learning outcomes in business education based on the marketing, resource, opportunity, interpersonal, learning, and strategic skills that are useful in the value creation process. Literature contributing to the linkage between business education and the value creating attitudes identifies the following themes

of attitudes as positive: value creation passion/inspiring entrepreneurial passion (Fisher *et al.*, 2008), business education identity/believing in value creation (Krueger, 2005, 2007), innovativeness/novel thoughts and actions (Krueger, 2005; Murnieks, 2007).

Creativity Competency for Value Creation

The multivariate approach defines four main components for creativity: a cognitive factor (e.g., intelligence or knowledge), a conative factor (e.g., personality or motivation), an emotional factor (the impact of emotional traits on creative potential), and an environmental factor (e.g., familial or school environments) (Ahmadi, & Besançon, 2017). In this context, more than ever, Business Education Students may need some abilities to adapt themselves to the uncertain future. More specifically, developing new competencies is needed (Sternberg, 2015), allowing them to offer new solutions for a peaceful future. Creativity seems to be one of the core components of these new abilities and is considered as an asset for value creation and societal development (Barbot, Lubart & Besançon 2016). Although creativity is widely recognized as an asset for society, it remains a fuzzy concept and there are many definitions of this competency in the literature (Sternberg, 2015). For some authors, creativity is “a novelty that is useful” (Sternberg, 2015); “the production of novel and useful ideas by an individual or small group of individual working together” (Barbot, Lubart and Besançon 2016); or the ability to produce novel and adapted solutions in a specific context (Lubart, Mouchiroud, Tordjman, & Zenasni 2015). In these definitions, the focus is put on the produce and seem to lead on a general agreement of the nature of creativity for value creation (Mumford, 2003). For El-Murad and West (2004), today most of the definitions of creativity combine the ideas of “novelty,” “appropriateness,” and “usefulness.” In this study, the researcher chooses the present creativity as the process of having original ideas that have value (Robinson & Aronica, 2015) and as an ability which can lead to major discoveries or simple creative production in everyday life (Beghetto & Kaufman, 2014).

Innovative Competency for Value Creation

The term “Innovation” is always linked to the insertion, implementation or development of an idea, product or service for the purpose of utility in society. Given its amplitude, different types of innovation were defined by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD 2016) as the following: a) product innovation is the application of an idea or service that has undergone substantial development, the feasibility of which may be related to its functionality or other techniques that make new uses for that idea or service possible; b) process innovation, referring to the development of new methods to achieve a given production; c) organizational innovation, or new types of organization or means of administering organizations; and d) marketing innovation, whereby new methods are used to obtain the development of products and their associated packaging, forms of cost and promotional publicity. The success of value creation champions strongly depends on their ability to innovate and create new knowledge/product. This is largely based on the knowledge, experience and individual dispositional abilities (i.e. the competencies) (Smith, Collins, Clark, 2005). Innovation has been valued as a necessary individual characteristic in the globalized world. Taken as a concept of multidisciplinary interest, research on this phenomenon has been developed in several areas of knowledge including administration, education, economics, psychology and sociology, among others. As a concept, innovation has been defined as the development of the product or practice of new and useful ideas to benefit individuals, teams, organizations or a broader range of society (Bledow, Frese, Erz, & Farr 2009). Then, there is the

need to clarify that innovation is not just a matter of coming up with a new idea but also requires a valuable product. In this case, “product” is not limited to a tangible object but can also be seen as a process to increase production and reduce costs in a way not yet tested in that specific context (Cropley, Kaufman & Corpley 2011). The distinction between product or process innovation is based on the social impact of each of these terms. While product innovation has a clear effect on the economy and job creation, process innovation must be looked at relative to its ability to bring a cost reduction, the time require for a given activity to be completed, or a significant gain in effectiveness to provide some type of service (Mello 2009). Understood in this way, innovation would involve the transformation or application of a concept into something that might have commercial value or that could be used by a wide range of people (Verissimo 2009).

Problem Solving Competency for Value Creation

Problem solving competency is the ability to solve problems by analyzing situations and apply critical thinking in order to resolve problems and decide on courses of action and implement the solutions developed in order to overcome problems and constraints (Letmathe & Schinner, 2017). A business is built on the problems (needs and wants) of customers and without these; there will be no business at all. Erol *et al.* (2016), highlight the importance of network and problem-solving competencies as the increasing complexity and scope of production processes “require a mind-set that is oriented towards building and maintaining networks of experts to be able to cooperate ad-hoc in finding appropriate solutions for particular problems for value creation (Erol *et al.* 2016). Also drawing attention to the increasing importance of creative problem-solving competencies, Letmathe and Schinner (2017), emphasize that in the digital industrial age employees will be less responsible for carrying out routine tasks and will be more involved with ad-hoc problem solving instead (Letmathe & Schinner, 2017). As many of the problems are unstructured, and complex, employees will not be able to solve all problems individually, network competence is needed to solve them collaboratively (Letmathe & Schinner, 2017). Based on a survey involving 335 German mechanical and plant engineering companies (which can mostly be considered to be value creation champions) a recent study showed that digital innovations are likely to take place at the boundaries of different disciplines and therefore require competencies that allow interdisciplinary and collaborative work (Kinkel, Rahn, Rieder, Lerch, & Jäger, 2016). The study found that – besides specific IT-related competencies – the following three nontechnical competencies were rated most valuable by the companies: (1) the ability to quickly grasp the business models and potential problems of customers, (2) to solve those problems creatively and (3) the ability to think and work using systematic and holistic ways of thinking (Kinkel, *et al.*, 2016).

Personnel Management Competency for Value Creation

One of the first authors to talk about the concept of ‘competencies’ was McClelland in several studies related to professional success (Morand, 2001). He defines personnel Management competencies as characteristics that are causally related to effective and/or superior job performance. An individual’s performance is assessed in terms of specific actions or behaviour indicators. Thirdly, Bertoncelj (2010) defines them as an observable behaviour that leads to success in a particular task or function. Furthermore, when that particular task or function is a personnel management competency function, he called it ‘managerial competence’. Bertoncelj (2010); Morand (2001) specify that the competencies are observable and habitual behaviours, introducing the idea of habit or repetition of certain behaviours.

Recently, Wright and Goodstein (2007) developed a new model of personnel management competencies emphasizing constructs such as courage, justice and temperance, recovering the idea of character for the theory of management. More recently, other authors like Bertoneclj (2010) have studied the co-native component of competencies of managers, developing a new manager's competencies framework. Lara and Salas-Vallina (2017) provide an update of the personnel Management competencies framework with the introduction of the mediating role of organisational learning in the relation between personnel managerial competencies, innovation and engagement for value creation. Personnel Management competencies refer to habitual observable behaviours. Each aspect of this definition must be clarified. First, a behaviour is neither a personality trait nor temperament character or knowledge. This first term directs our study of personnel management competencies towards action for value creation. Secondly, observable means that it is possible to measure not only their development level at a certain moment, but also their progress and learning process for value creation acumen. Thirdly, habitual means related to the acquisition of new behavioural habits, which implies the possibility of continues learning to enhance value creation (Prado-Gasco, Pardo, & Perez-Campos, 2017).

Methodology

In the present study, a descriptive survey research design was to examine competencies require by undergraduate business education students for economic value creation in north eastern Nigeria. A descriptive survey method is used when a researcher is interested in studying the opinions, feelings, and thoughts of the respondents about a particular situation (Fisher, 2010). This method enables the researchers to collect and analyse quantitative data. Hence, a descriptive survey design is appropriate for achieving the objective of this study. The population of this study comprised 527 registered small and medium scale entrepreneurs in North East Nigeria that deal directly with manufacturing of goods through transformation of raw materials in to finished goods (SMEDAN 2021). The choice of this population was in line with the argument of Ezenwafor, and Enemu (2016); Onwuchekwa, Ejike, and Mgbemena, (2017) that business owners/mangers from their wealth of experience are information rich to determine the require or needed skills for establishing small and medium enterprises. The authors also argued that they employment generating agencies that can provide better information for competencies require for self-reliance or employment generating activities. The sample size for this study consist of 262 owners/mangers of SMEs that deal with manufacturing (transformation of raw materials in finished goods) only in the study area. The sample was statistically determined using GPower, a statistical procedure used for determining the appropriate minimum sample size required for a study. A simple random sampling technique was used in the study because this sampling technique is believed to produce samples which are free from bias (Sambo, 2008).

The variables of this study were measured using Business Education Students Competencies required for economic Value Creation Questionnaire. The questionnaire was adapted from previous studies (Gyeongsang, 2017; Bernard, 2013). The research consists of two (4) variables: creativity competencies (7 items), innovative competencies (10 items), problem solving competencies (9 items) and personnel management competencies (10 items). In this study, the Likert scale was adopted for all the items, the respondents were asked to indicate their responses to each question on a five-rating scale. The five- rating scale used in this study is as follows: Very highly require (VHR) =5; Highly require (HR) =4; Require (R)=3; Fairly require (FR) =2 and Not Require (NR) =1. To ensure the reliability of instrument of the present study, the pilot test was conducted with 30 registered owners of manufacturing small and

medium scale enterprises in Kano state, Nigeria. Because the state is outside the study area but the respondents have similar characteristics with the sample of this study. In this study, the reliability of the instrument was assessed using Cronbach alpha, the reliability coefficients of the four variable are; creativity competencies (0.92), innovative competencies (0.91), problem solving competencies (0.95), and personnel management competency (0.94). The results suggested that the instrument is reliable based on the recommendation given by Hair *et al.* (2017). According to them Cronbach alpha coefficient of at least .70 is considered satisfactory and acceptable. Finally, for cleaning of data and analysis, SPSS 23 was used throughout the process to run the mean and standard deviation.

Findings

The results of descriptive statistics documented in 1 indicated that all the items of creativity competencies require by undergraduate business education students for value creation are having mean scores of above 3.00. The mean scores of creativity competencies items are ranging from 3.63 to 3.84. The grand mean of creativity competencies is 3.74 with a standard deviation of .578. The result indicated that the creativity competencies are highly required by undergraduate business education students for economic value creation. The result further implies that undergraduate business education students highly require creativity competencies for value creation and self-reliant within the society.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of creativity competencies require by undergraduate business education students for economic value creation in North East Nigeria.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Specialize in coming up with lots of economic value ideas.	3.63	1.130	HR
2	Creating product based on economic ideas generated	3.81	.872	HR
3	See problems as economic value opportunities rather than as issues	3.84	.917	HR
4	Ability to create or manufacture goods using available resources.	3.71	.906	HR
5	Ability to develop creative economic value ideas to solve problems.	3.67	.884	HR
6	Ability to invent	3.72	.944	HR
7	Ability to create new product to meet customers' need.	3.82	1.006	HR
Grand Mean		3.74	.578	HR

Note: Very highly require (VHR), Highly require (HR), Require (R), Fairly require (FR) Not Require (NR)

The descriptive statistics of innovative competencies require by undergraduate business education students for economic value creation in table 2 revealed that the mean score of respondents in all the items of innovative competencies are greater than 3.00. That is, all the items are having the mean score of above 3.0 (see, table 2) with a grand mean of 3.60 and standard deviation of .435. This suggested that undergraduate business education students highly require innovative competencies for economic value creation in North East Nigeria.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of innovative competencies require by undergraduate business education students for economic value creation in North East Nigeria.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Persistent in achieving innovation goals	3.84	.910	HR
2	Build diverse cooperative networks for business	3.87	.816	HR
3	Capability to fit product or service to customer needs	3.65	.970	HR
4	Familiar with making something new or different for economic value.	3.46	1.063	HR
5	Enjoy exploiting new ideas to solve economic problems	3.43	1.062	HR
6	Capability to make something better for economic value	3.43	1.047	HR
7	Device diverse useful ideas for business	3.61	1.090	HR
8	Interested in an innovative startup business	3.55	1.073	HR
9	Start-up intention with innovative ideas for economic benefit	3.52	1.053	HR
10	Regard start-up as a challenge for economic value creation goal	3.69	1.083	HR
Grand Mean		3.60	.435	HR

Note: Very highly require (VHR), Highly require (HR), Require (R), Fairly require (FR) Not Require (NR)

The descriptive statistic was carried out to ascertain mean response of business practitioners on the extent to which problems solving competencies are required by undergraduate business education students for economic value creation in North East Nigeria. The statistical evidence documented in table 3 showed that mean scores of all the nine items are above 3.00, while the grand mean of problems solving competencies was found to be 3.67 with a standard deviation of .400. This implies that undergraduate business education students highly required problems solving competencies for economic value creation in North East Nigeria.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of problems solving competencies require by undergraduate business education students for economic value creation in North East Nigeria.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Ability to choose an economic value solution from different alternatives to solve problem.	4.04	.666	HR
2	After an economic value solution has been implemented, look for ways to improve the idea to avoid future problems	3.91	.805	HR
3	Strive to look at economic value problems from different perspectives and generate multiple solutions.	3.68	.950	HR
4	Evaluate potential economic solutions carefully and thoroughly against a predefined standard.	3.44	1.022	HR
5	Systematically search for economic issues that may become problems in the future as potential values.	3.34	.999	HR
6	Ask oneself lots of different questions about the nature of economic problem.	3.40	.932	HR
7	Ability explores potential economic solutions.	3.60	.915	HR
8	Ability to analyze the information needed to find economic solution to a problem that needs to be solved.	3.77	.936	HR
9	Making economic value decision is a means to the end of problem-solving process.	3.82	.949	HR
	Grand Mean	3.67	.400	HR

Note: Very highly require (VHR), Highly require (HR), Require (R), Fairly require (FR) Not Require (NR)

The descriptive statistics was carried out to ascertain mean response of business practitioners on the extent to which personnel management competencies are required by undergraduate business education students for economic value creation in North East Nigeria. The statistical evidence documented in table 4 showed that mean scores of all the ten items are above 3.00, while the grand mean of personnel management competencies was found to be 3.63 with a standard deviation of .393. This implies that undergraduate business education students highly require personnel management competencies for value creation in North East Nigeria.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics of personnel management competencies require by undergraduate business education students for economic value creation in North East Nigeria.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Management of employees' job activities for value creation	3.88	.844	HR
2	Motivate employees to enhance economic value creation	3.82	.827	HR
3	Engage successfully in facilitation of economic value negotiation efforts	3.66	.940	HR
4	Demonstrate effective communication skills in conveying economic vision	3.51	.879	HR
5	Demonstrate effective economic goal-setting actions to subordinates to emulate.	3.52	.921	HR
6	Structure economic idea generating activities in a fashion that is intellectually stimulating for subordinates.	3.43	1.036	HR
7	Competent in implementing reward systems to stimulate economic creative behaviour in subordinates.	3.41	1.020	HR
8	Have the necessary economic value creation mentor/coaching skills.	3.50	.982	HR
9	Constantly inspire subordinates to be curious and challenge the status quo.	3.72	.908	HR
10	Having diverse economic value perspectives.	3.81	.908	HR
	Grand Mean	3.63	.393	HR

Note: Very highly require (VHR), Highly require (HR), Require (R), Fairly require (FR) Not Require (NR)

Discussion

The findings of research question one revealed that undergraduate business education students highly require creativity competencies for value creation in North East Nigeria. The finding is consistent with Adeagbo, Adekunle, Fatai, and Lasisi (2020) who reported that creativity competency is highly require for self-reliance among business education graduate in Oyo state. In a related study, Nwagwu (2016) confirmed that creativity competencies are highly required for job creation by Business education students in Ebonyi state. The findings of research question two indicated that undergraduate business education students highly require innovative competencies for value creation in North-Eastern Nigeria. The findings concurred with arguments in the existing literature, such as the study conducted by Amua and Amaewhule (2019) in Rivers state, which indicated that business education students in the state require innovative competencies for self-reliance and achievement need. The findings also consistent with the study of Shirka, Nor, and Gimba (2018) in revealed that Technical / Engineering students of Polytechnic need innovative competencies to be self-reliant. Similarly, Candy (2017), found that the business education students in Ebonyi State University highly require innovative competencies for self-reliance which is consistent with the present study. Moreover, Ezenwafor, Faben, and Olaniyi (2017) study revealed that business education graduates highly needed innovative competencies for entrepreneurial development and sustenance in South west which concurred with the finding of the present study.

Furthermore, Nwagwu (2016) study among tertiary institutions in Ebonyi state revealed a similar finding which indicated that business education students highly require innovative skills for job creation.

The findings of research question three indicated that undergraduate business education students highly require problem solving competencies for value creation in North East Nigeria. The findings concurred with arguments in the existing literature, such as the study conducted by Robinson, Vbiugie, Osigbeme (2021) in Edo and Delta State, the study revealed business educators perceived that business graduate require problem solving competencies to a very high extent for job performance. Similarly, Ezenwafor, Faben, and Olaniyi (2017) study which revealed that business education graduates highly needed problem solving competencies for entrepreneurial development and sustenance in South west which is consistent with the empirical evidences of the present study. Finally, the findings of research question four revealed that undergraduate business education students highly require personnel management competencies for value creation in North East Nigeria. The findings consistent with the arguments in the existing literature, such as the study conducted by Banjo, Falola, Ganiyu, and Kabiru (2017) in Oyo state, which indicated that the students highly require personnel management competencies for entrepreneurship. In another study by Candy (2017), found that business education students in Ebonyi State University highly require personnel management competencies for self-reliance which agrees with empirical evidences in the current study. Moreover, Ezenwafor, and Enemuo (2016) study revealed that management competencies are highly needed for entrepreneurship in South west which agrees with the findings of the current study.

Conclusion

This research work examines the competencies of undergraduate business education students for economic value creation in North-Eastern Nigeria. This study proved empirically that creativity, innovative, problem solving, and personnel management competencies are highly required by undergraduate business education students for economic value creation. Therefore, the mind of business education graduates can be change from moving office to office in search of unavailable white collar jobs which always increases the level of the country's unemployment to economic value creation where graduates can establish their own business ventures to create values for themselves and others, thereby contributing to the economy and reducing unemployment rate in the country. This could be achieved when business education students are well exposed to creativity, innovative, problem solving, and personnel management competencies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. The regulatory bodies such as national university commission through quality assurance should ensure that business education students are well exposed to creativity, innovative, problem solving, and personnel management competencies.
2. The regulatory bodies should put more emphasis on creativity, innovative, problem solving, and personnel management competencies in the curriculum of undergraduate business education students.
3. School management from time to time should sensitize business education students on the significance of creativity, innovative, problem solving, and personnel management competencies towards economic value creation among students after graduation.

References

- Adeagbo, S., Adekunle, P., Fatai, O., & Lasisi B. (2020). Promoting self-reliance through the enhancement of creativity in Business Education Students in Oyo State Tertiary Institutions for Sustainable Development. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education*, 7(1), 43-56.
- Akhere, D. (2013). Innovation in Business Education Programme at the Tertiary Institutions: Business Education Book of Ready. *Journal of Business Education* 4(1), 431-562.
- Ahmadi, N. & Besançon, M. (2017). Creativity as a Stepping Stone towards Developing Other Competencies in Classrooms 2(1), 541.
- Amoor S. S. & Udoh A. A. (2018). The role secretarial education in Nigeria economic development. *Journal of educational research and development* 3(1), 294-298
- Amuah, A. A. & Amaewhule, W. (2019). Determination of Entrepreneurship Skills for Self Reliance of Business Education Students in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research* 7(3), 37-45
- Barbot, B. Lubart T. I., & Besançon M., (2016). Peaks, slumps, and bumps': individual differences in the development of creativity in children and adolescents," *New Directions for Child and Adolescent Development*, 151(1), 33-45.
- Beghetto, R. A., & Kaufman, A. (2014). Classroom contexts for creativity. *High Ability Studies*, 25(1), 53-69.
- Bledow, R., Frese, M., Anderson, N., Erez, M., & Farr, J. (2009). A dialectic perspective on innovation: Conflicting demands, multiple pathways, and ambidexterity. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 2(3), 305-337.
- Bertoncelj, A. (2010). Managers' competencies framework: A study of conative component. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 23(4), 91-101.
- Bernard, D. (2013). The Development of an Innovation Leadership Questionnaire by Swart Supervisor: Prof DJ Malan December
- Banjo J. O. S., Falola O. Ganiyu A. & Kabiru Y. (2017). Effects of Managerial Skills require in Entrepreneurship among Undergraduates in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Makerere Journal of Higher Education*, 9 (1), 97 – 101.
- Candy, A. (2017). Entrepreneurial Skills Needed by Business Education Students for Self reliance Ebonyi State University. A Thesis research work. Unpublished
- Cheong, K.-C., Hill, C., Fernandez-Chung, R., & Leong, Y.-C. (2015). Employing the 'unemployable': Employer perceptions of Malaysian graduates. *Studies in Higher Education*, 4(1), 2253-2270.
- Cropley, D. H., Kaufman, J. C., & Cropley, A. (2011). Measuring creativity for innovation management. *Journal of Technology Management and Innovation*, 6(3), 13-30.
- El-Murad, J. & West, D. (2004). "The definition and measurement of creativity: what do we know?" *Journal of Advertising Research*, 44(2), 188-201
- Erol, S. Jäger, A. Hold, P. Ott, K. & Sihm, W. (2016). Tangible Industry 4.0: A Scenario-Based Approach to Learning for the Future of Production, *Procedia CIRP*, 54(1), 13-18.
- Ezenwafor, J. I., & Enemu, A. U. (2016). Marketing and Management Competencies Require for Successful Entrepreneurship as Perceived by Officers of Employment Generation Agencies in South-East Nigeria. *European Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*. 1(1), 2501 - 9988.
- Ezenwafor, J. I. Justina I. & Onokpaunu, D. Michel O. (2017). Teaching of Soft Skills in Tertiary Institutions for SMES Operation in Nigeria 11(3), 2454-2326.

- Ezenwafor, J. I. Faben & Olaniyi. O. N. (2017). Ratings Skills Needed by Business Education Graduates for Entrepreneurial Development in Southwest Nigeria. *ESSEC Business School, ESSEC Business School,4(1), 35-39.*
- Fisher, S., Graham, M., & Compeau, M. (2008). "Starting from Scratch: Understanding the Learning Outcomes of Undergraduate Entrepreneurship Education," in *Entrepreneurial Learning: Conceptual Frameworks and Applications*, eds R. T. Harrison and C. Leitch (New York, NY: Routledge).
- Filipowicz, G. (2004). *Zarządzanie kompetencjami zawodowymi*. Warszawa: PWE
- Grosemans, I., Coertjens, L., & Kyndt, E. (2017). Exploring learning and Fit in the Transition From Higher Education to the Labour Market: A Systematic Review. *Educational Research Review J, 21, 67–84*
- Gupta, O., & Roos, G. (2001). Mergers and Acquisitions Through an Intellectual Capital Perspective. *Journal of Intellectual Capital, 2(3), 297–309*
- Gyeongsang, Z. (2017) Relationship Between Entrepreneurs' Managerial Competencies and Innovative Start-up Intentions in University Students: an Iranian Case. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship 21(3), 1939-4675*
- Hair, J. F. Ringle, C. M. & Sarstedt M. L. (2011). The Use of Partial Least Squares (PLS) to Address Marketing Management Topics Advanced in International Marketing. *Journal of marketing Research. Papers.ssrn.com 20(1), 277-319.*
- Heijke, H., Meng, C., & Ris, C. (2003). Fitting to the Job: The Role of Generic and Vocational Competencies in Adjustment and Performance. *Labour Economics, 10(2), 215–229.*
- Kinkel, S. Rahn,V Rieder,V Lerch,V & Jäger, A. (2016). Digital-vernetztes Denken in der Produktion, Institut für Lernen und Innovation in Netzwerken, Hochschule Karlsruhe | Fraunhofer-Institut für System-und Innovationsforschung ISI, Karlsruhe.
- Krueger, N. F. (2005). "The Cognitive Psychology of Entrepreneurship," in *Handbook of Entrepreneurship Research: An Interdisciplinary Survey and Introduction*, eds Z. J. Acs and D. B. Audretsch (New York, NY: Springer).
- Krueger, N. F. (2007). What Lies Beneath? The Experiential Essence of Entrepreneurial Thinking. *Entrepreneursh. Theory Pract. 31(1), 123–138.*
- Kyndt, E., & Baert, H. (2015). Entrepreneurial Competencies: Assessment and Predictive Value For Entrepreneurship. *Journal of Vocational Behavior, 90, 13–25*
- Lara, F. J., & Salas-Vallina, A. (2017). Managerial Competencies, Innovation and Engagement in SMEs: The Mediating Role of Organizational Learning. *Journal of Business Research, 79(2), 152–160.*
- Leoni, R. (2014). Graduate Employability and the Development of Competencies. The Incomplete Reform of the "Bologna Process". *International Journal of Manpower, 35(4), 448–469.*
- Letmathe, P & Schinner, M. (2017), Competence Management in the Age of Cyber Physical Systems, in: Industrial Internet of Things: Cyber manufacturing Systems Jeschke, S. Brecher, C. Song, H. Rawat D.B. (eds.), , *Springer International, Cham, 595-614.*
- Lubart, T. Mouchiroud, C. Tordjman S., & Zenasni F., (2015). *Psychologie de la créativité*, Armand Colin, Paris, France,.
- Maigida,F. J., (2012) "Assessment of the Role of TVET in the Reduction of Unemployment among Youths in Nigeria," *J. Technol. Educ. Res., 5,(1), 6–12,*
- Male, S. (2010). Generic Engineering Competencies: A Review and Modelling Approach. *Education Research and Perspectives, 37(1), 25–51*

- Man, T. W. Y. (2007). Understanding Entrepreneurial Learning A Competency Approach. The *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 8(3), 189-198.
- Man, T. W. Y., Lau, T. & Chan, K. (2002). The Competitiveness of Small and Medium Enterprises: A Conceptualization with Focus on Entrepreneurial Competencies. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 17(2), 123-142.
- Markman, G. D. (2007). Entrepreneurs' Competencies. *The Psychology of Entrepreneurship*, 67- 92. Martin, B. C.,
- Mazzucato M (2018). *The Value of Everything: Making and Taking in the Global Economy*. Allen Lane, London.
- Mello, M. T. L. (2009). Propriedade Intelectual E concorrência. *Revista Brasileira de Inovação*, 8(2), 371-402.
- Miller, T. L., Wesley, C. L., & Williams, D. E. (2012). Educating the Minds of Caring Hearts: Comparing the Views of Practitioners and Educators on the Importance of Social Entrepreneurship Competencies. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 11(3), 349-370
- Mitchelmore, S., & Rowley, J. (2010). Entrepreneurial competencies: A literature review and development agenda. *Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 16(2), 92- 111
- Morand, D. A. (2001). The Emotional Intelligence of Managers: Assessing the Construct Validity of a Nonverbal Measure of "People Skills". *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 16(1), 21-33
- Morris, M. H., Webb, J. W., Fu, J., & Singhal, S. (2013). A Competency-based Perspective on Entrepreneurship Education: Conceptual and Empirical Insights. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 51(3), 352-369.
- Mumford, M. D. (2003). "Where Have We Been, Where Are We Going? Taking Stock in Creativity Research," *Creativity Research Journal*, 15 (2), 107-120,
- Murnieks, C. Y. (2007). *Who Am I? The Quest for an Entrepreneurial Identity and an Investigation of its Relationship to Entrepreneurial Passion and Goal-Setting*. Ph.D. Thesis, University of Colorado, Boulder, CO.
- NBS (March, 2021). National Bureau of Statistics. Unemployment 3rd quarter Survey report (March)[Brochure]. Abuja, Nigerian Capital Territory: Author.
- Nkamnebe, A.D (2008). Challenges of Vocational and Technical Education in Contributing to the Attainment of 7 Point Agenda, Paper Presented at the 3rd National Conference of the School of Business and Technical Education Oha, Kwara State.
- Nicolescu, L., & P[acaron]un, C. (2009). Relating Higher Education with the Labour Market: Graduates' Expectations and Employers' Requirements. *Tertiary Education and Management*, 15(1), 17-33.
- Nwagwu, L. N (2016). Assessment of Job Creation Skills Available to Business Education Students in Tertiary Institutions in Ebonyi State, *Nigeria Journal of Educational Policy and Entrepreneurial Research (JEPER)* 3(7), 129-135
- OECD. (2019). *The Future of Education and Skills: Education 2030*; Directorate for Education and Skills: Paris, France, from <http://www.oecd.org/site/innovationstrategy/defininginnovation.htm>
- OECD (2016). *Entrepreneurship at a glance*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
- Okoli B. E. (2013) A Case for Entrenchment of ICT Literacy in the Business Education Programme. *J voc. Adult Edu.*, 7(2) 82-87
- Osioma, B. C. (2015). Education and Human Capital Development: Changing Global Dynamics and Skill. *International journal of academic researchers (IJAR)*. 1(1) 5-8

- Onwuchekwa, F. C. Ejike, D. C. & Mgbemena, G. C. (2017). The Role of Entrepreneurial Competencies in Promoting Entrepreneurship in Nigeria: A Study of Practicing Entrepreneurs in Anambra State, Nigeria *AFRREV 11(2)*, 46.
- Oziengbe, U.V (2009). Industrializing the Nigeria Society Through Creative Skill Acquisition Vocational and Technical Education Programme. *Academic journal* <http://www.academicjournals.org/INGOJISSN> 1(22), 1993 - 8225.
- Pabian, P., Šima, K., & Kynčilová, L. (2011). Humboldt Goes to the Labour Market: How Academic Higher Education Fuels Labour Market Success in the Czech Republic. *Journal of Education and Work*, 24, 95–118.
- Prado-Gascó, V., Pardo, I. Q., & Pérez-Campos, C. (2017). Knowledge Management and Organizational Culture in a Software Development Enterprise. *Journal of Small Business Strategy*, 27(1), 37–50.
- Rasmussen, E., Mosey, S. & Wright, M. (2011). The Evolution of Entrepreneurial Competencies: A Longitudinal Study of University Spin-Off Venture Emergence. *Journal of Management Studies*, 48(6), 1314-1345.
- Robinson O. O. Vbiugie T. & Osigbeme, J. (2021) Competencies Require of Business Education Graduates' Job Performance in Edo and Delta States of Nigeria *Zambia Journal of Education* /<https://medicine.unza.zm/index.php/index> 6 (1) 22
- Robinson K. and Aronica L.,(2015). *Creative Schools the grassroots revolution that's transforming education*, Penguin Books,
- Rubin, R. S., & Dierdorff, E. C. (2017). How Relevant is the MBA? Assessing the Alignment of Require Curricula and Require Managerial Competencies. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 8(2), 208–224.
- Sambo, A. A. (2008). *Research methods in education*. Edo: Stirling-Horden Publishers.
- Samuel B. E. (2020). Entrepreneurship for Self Employment in the Face of Unemployment and White Collar Job among Nigerian Graduate. *international Journal of youth and Entrepreneurship Development* 2(1), 2449-30342.
- Sánchez, J. C. (2011). University Training for Entrepreneurial Competencies: Its Impact on Intention of Venture Creation. *Int. Entrepreneursh. Manag. J.* 7, 239–254.
- SMEDAN. (2021). Survey report on Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Nigeria. Abuja: Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria. A publication of Federal Republic of Nigeria. <http://www.smedan.gov.ng>.
- Shirka K. J., Nor, F. M. A., & Gimba D. (2018). Self-Reliance Through innovation and Entrepreneurship Competency of Technical/Engineering Polytechnic Students in Nigeria. *Journal Pendidikan Teknologi dan Kejuruan*, 24(2), 185-191.
- Smith, J K.G., Collins, C. & Clark, J K.D. (2005) Existing Knowledge, Knowledge Creation Capability, and the Rate of New Product Introduction in HighTechnology Firms, *Academy of Management Journal* 482, 346-357.
- Smith, B., & Morse, E. (2005). *Entrepreneurial Competencies: Literature Review and Best Practices*. Ottawa: Small Business Policy Branch, Industry Canada.
- Sternberg, R. J. (2015). “Teaching for Creativity: The Sounds of Silence,” *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 9 (2),115–117.
- Strijbos, J., Engels, N., & Struyven, K. (2015). Criteria and Standards of Generic Competences at Bachelor Degree Level: A review study. *Educational Research Review*, 14, 18– 32.

- Schweitzer, K. (2016). Business Education; Types of Business School Degrees. . *Journal of Business Management*, 33(4), 928–958.
- Tomlison, C.A. (2016). Meaning of Business Education; Contributions of Business Education to National Development: Perception of Academic Staff and Students of Nwafor Orizu College of Education Nsugbe 3(1), 78-84.
- UNESCO (2014). Annual Report 2013: UNESCO Institute for Education.
- Uddin P. S. O. (2013). Causes, Effects and Solution to Youth Unemployment in Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trend in Economics and management sciences* 4(1), 4.
- Veríssimo, G. (2009). Inovação: um turbulento e pra-zero desafio. In Z. G. Giglio, S. M. Wechsler, & D. Bragotto (Orgs.), *Da criatividade à inovação* (157-166). Campinas: Papyrus.
- Vučetić, A. Š. (2018). Differences in Perception of the Importance of Generic Competencies Among Destination Regions. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 31(1), 1240-1257,
- Wright, T., & Goodstein, J. (2007). Character is Not Dead in Management Research: A Review of Individual Character and Organizational-level Virtue. *Journal of Management*, 33(6), 928–958
- Young, J., & Chapman, E. (2010). Generic Competency Frameworks: A Brief Historical Overview. *Education Research and Perspectives*, 37, 1–24